

ANTHROPONYM AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

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Abstract. *In this article, the scientific research conducted as an object of linguistic research on anthroponomic terms is gradually shown. Also, the opinions and views of scientists on this subject were studied.*

Keywords: *linguistic fact, structural linguistics, anthroponym, person, research, object.*

In recent years, serious attention has been paid to systematic research in linguistics. The peculiarity of these studies is that they do not approach linguistic facts independently, but pay attention to the discovery of the essence hidden under each phenomenon. The researcher's attention is more focused on elucidating the relationship between linguistic phenomena.

F. de Saussure, who is considered the father of structural linguistics, focused the attention of linguists on revealing the relationship between linguistic units and showed the existence of paradigmatic and syntagmatic types of relationship. Therefore, based on the above considerations, the objects that are denoted by nouns in the language are material, natural and artificial, imaginary, real and legendary, secular or religious, they are on land and water, on the surface of the earth or underground or, on the contrary, they are objects located in space.

This article not only studies anthroponyms as an object of linguistic research, but also focuses on their motivation. In turn, anthroponyms are lexemes with the archetype "person", to reveal their meaningful groups, the factors that cause their creation in linguistics in general, their general and specific, unifying and differentiating aspects are analyzed. Explanatory dictionaries recognize the use of the word "personnel" in relation to employees, office workers, and individuals. Accordingly, anthroponyms generalized with the lexeme "person" belong to the field of personality. In Uzbek language, units belonging to this microfield are observed at different levels of the language.

Onomastics is an independent branch of linguistics that studies common nouns, their characteristics, origin, history, as well as changes that have occurred in the course of long-term use and the influence of other languages on them. In the framework of linguistics, onomastics reflects historical, geographical, ethnographic, social, cultural and literary significance.

In different eras, people felt the need to give special names to objects, places, creatures and people in their environment, in order to distinguish them and separate them from each other [1].

The naming of an object, thing, and event by taking it individually began to spread to all the things required by the needs of life, and the names that are now used as proper nouns in the language increased. The mentioned vital need also created the need to distinguish people who live in a clan, tribe, group, and belong to the same clan and family.

According to historians and ethnographers, there was a common name of a clan and a tribe, the name of a person belonging to that clan or tribe corresponded to the name of the clan or tribe, that is, a person belonging to an ethnic group is called a clan. The names of clans or tribes consist of the name of an animal or bird that the ethnic group considers sacred and worships. Gradually, this tradition changed, and each person who was a member of a clan or tribe was called by a

separate name or nickname. In this way, the first proper nouns of a person, the names of people, appear [2].

In the process of research conducted by a group of onomastics scientists, as a result of the classification of nouns into different groups according to their content, several independent sections appeared in the structure of onomastics. Western scientists such as F. Mikloshich, P. Skok, E. Muka, K. Moshinsky, S. Rospond, S. A. Kosporsky, A. V. Nikitin conducted research on these issues and proposed various classifications [3].

Among them, A. Bach, one of the onomastic scientists, classified all existing proper nouns according to their objects as follows:

1. Names of living creatures;
2. Names of objects related to time and space, means of movement, works of visual art, astrogeographical and space objects;
3. Names of community institutions;
4. Action names (m-n, dance and games);
5. Names of thoughts, ideas (literary works, military and other plans);
6. Names of musical works [3].

The famous Russian scientist A. V. Superanskaya, who made an important contribution to the field of onomastics, while studying proper nouns based on their meaning, the object they denote, emphasizes the need to study them in different groups and divides proper noun groups into 19 types.

Azerbaijani scientist A. M. Gurbanov defines 7 groups of nouns: anthroponyms, ethnonyms, toponyms, hydronyms, zoonyms, cosmonyms, ktomotonyms [4].

Among them, it is determined that the department of anthroponymy, which studies the personal names of people, is of special importance.

"Anthroponymy" is one of the branches of onomastics, which studies the names of people, their origin, distribution, practical use in society, as well as the structure and development of anthroponymic systems.

We can see famous nouns, nicknames, relative names and different ways of naming another person as the source of "Anthroponymy".

Anthroponymy, as a branch of linguistics, is divided into 2:

- theoretical anthroponymy;
- practical anthroponymy.

Theoretical anthroponomy - studies the origin, development of anthroponyms, their structure, anthroponomic systems, anthroponomic history of one or another nation, the influence of languages on anthroponymy.

Practical anthroponymy studies the problems related to the criteria of names, the use of the same name in different languages, and deals with creating anthroponomic dictionaries.

Anthroponomic information is important for other areas of linguistics, including sociology, ethnography, and the study of people's history [5].

According to the definition of the Russian scientist O. S. Akhmanova, "Anthroponym" means the Greek "anthropos" - (man) and "onyma" - (name), that is, personal names of people [6].

Anthroponym is a personal name or a combination of several personal names that identifies people.

In the main scientific sources, including "Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary", anthroponyms are divided into the following types:

- personal names (given at birth);
- patronymic [3];
- surname (first name);
- nickname;
- ratio;
- cryptonym (hidden names)
- names of heroes of works of art, folklore, legends, fairy tales;
- names derived from ethnonyms (peoples, nations, tribes) [7].

Taking into account the wide scope of the topic, this article covers 2 different types of this concept, i.e. in a narrow sense (only the name itself) and in a broad sense (combination of first name, last name, nickname).

Despite the fact that anthroponyms refer only to the naming of people, it is the only object that represents the complex spectrum of the category of names, which, in turn, reflects the history of culture, the characteristics of human psychology, traditions, etc.

A. V. Superanskaya analyzes anthroponyms into individual and group types. According to her:

Individual anthroponyms distinguish an individual from a community, and those related to group anthroponyms are studied by combining them into communities based on one or another character.

A. V. Superanskaya, in addition to the above, also divides anthroponyms into types such as micro and macro. As a result of applying this classification to Uzbek anthroponyms, the following can be noted:

- Micro anthroponyms are names that indicate individual characteristics of people. For example: Aynur, Mohinur.

- Macro anthroponyms include the names of certain communities, i.e. families, clans, dynasties. For example: Baburids, Timurids, Barlos [8].

The main object of anthroponymy, "name", is defined in the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan as follows: "A name is a name given to a child when the birth is registered. The name allows to separate individuals within the family, generation, neighborhood, community. Usually, the name of the baby is chosen by parents, relatives, and elderly people in the family. What kind of name to give depends on aesthetic and ethical principles, wishes of name choosers, imagination and world views, national characteristics, etc., is connected with religion. After Christianity came into being and became a monotheistic religion, the names of the prophets in the "Bible" became common names in many nations of the world. The spread of Islam led to an increase in names related to the concepts of this religion among the peoples of Central Asia, especially Uzbeks. Our people gave their children the beautiful names of Allah mentioned in the Holy Qur'an and the names of Prophet Muhammad. So, each name appears for a specific reason and has its own history, geographical distribution, territory and meaning [1]. "Various customs and traditions of naming have been preserved since ancient times."

Encyclopedia Britannica notes that names and their study are of scientific and historical importance and therefore of great interest. It turns out that even in the period of the primitive community, people had their own names, by which it was possible to call them and address them.

It is clear from this that anthroponyms are a particularly important part of the language vocabulary in people's lives. First of all, they are always actively used in various aspects of life. It can be defined as a single and, secondly, as a phenomenon affecting the spiritual, religious-aesthetic processes in person's life. Therefore, it is very important to study the anthroponymy of a particular language, including determining the place and importance of anthroponyms in the language dictionary, the meaning of anthroponyms and their etymological origin, structure, and their role in society.

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